

***Acontista cordillerae* Saussure, 1869 in Florida**

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Abstract. The first documentation of *Acontista cordillerae* Saussure, 1869 within the United States is established.

Introduction. Saussure first described *Acontista cordillerae* in 1869 from a single male specimen that was collected in Mexico. In 1894, Saussure & Zehntner assessed a series of *Acontista* from various locations within Latin America for their *Biologia Centrali-Americana* tome. Despite himself having described *cordillerae* twenty-five years earlier, Saussure failed to recognize the extreme variability in pigmentation among individuals of this species and introduced within this later work two new species, *mexicana* and *vitrea*, that were distinguished from *cordillerae* through differences in color. These authors further described two additional “variants” of *mexicana*, *inquinata* and *quadrifasciata*, that were also diagnosed by variation in pigmentation.

Kirby established Saussure & Zehntner’s *quadrifasciata* variant from Guatemala as an independent species in 1904 and provided the replacement name of *championi* for it, as the name *quadrifasciata* had already been used by Serville in 1839 to describe a different species of *Acontista* from Brazil. Giglio-Tos reiterated this designation in 1927 when he noted that *quadrifasciata* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894 was the name synonymized with *championi* by Kirby and “non *Mantis quadrifasciata* Serville, 1839.” Serville’s *quadrifasciata* from Brazil was later synonymized with *concinna* (Perty, 1833), a common Brazilian species.

In 1919, Hebard described *Acontiothespis iriodes*, a Colombian species that the author noted as a “diminutive and beautiful insect” that showed “nearest relationship to *A. cordillerae* and *A. vitrea*.” At the time of the establishment of this species, Hebard compared the male type specimen from Colombia to a series of both *cordillerae* and *vitrea* males from other locales. He found that within these later two species the distal portion of the forefemora are blackish-brown, whereas the forefemora of *iriodes* are “immaculate lettuce green”. Hebard erroneously suggested that “features of coloration are important as specific diagnostic characters” within this group and used the lack of forefemoral maculation in *iriodes* as a primary basis to diagnose his new species. He further differentiated *iriodes* from these other two species by noting that *vitrea* males

have longer wings and *cordillerae* males have colored wings, in comparison to the shorter, hyaline wings of *iriodes*.

In 2020, Rivera and Svenson examined the holotype of *iriodes* alongside conspecifics that had been collected near the Colombian type locality. Among the series of males examined were found both light and dark phase individuals, some with blackish maculation on the forefemora and some without such markings, as in the holotype specimen. Aside from these pigmentation differences, which were later shown to be an unreliable diagnostic character within *Acontista* due to the wide variation of interspecific coloration, the *iriodes* series were morphologically comparable to the co-occurring *cordillerae*. It was thus determined that the *iriodes* holotype male was merely an example of a light phase individual of *cordillerae*, therefore necessitating a synonymy. Additionally, these authors determined that Saussure & Zehntner's *mexicana*, *vitrea*, *inquinata* and *quadrifasciata*, as well as Kirby's replacement name *championi*, all represent color variations of *cordillerae*. However, in a notation provided in Fig. 42e of this same paper, Rivera & Svenson noted that "*championi* is a replacement name for *Acontista quadrifasciata* (Audinet-Serville, 1838); see Marshall, 1976)," which contradicts the body of their text on pages 117-118, wherein *quadrifasciata* Serville, 1838 is correctly listed as a junior synonym of *concinna* and not of *championi*, as their aberrant note suggests.

When referring back to Marshall's 1975 catalogue of types, we find that this author references Kirby's introduction of *championi* as a replacement name for *quadrifasciata* Saussure & Zehntner, 1894 but comments that this name "is a junior secondary homonym of *Acontista quadrifasciata* (Serville, [1838])." This conclusion is not representative of Kirby's 1904 designation of *championi* as the replacement name for Saussure & Zehntner's *quadrifasciata*, where we find on page 233 that Kirby lists Serville's *quadrifasciata* as a synonym of *concinna* and not *championi*. Thus, it would appear that Marshall drew an incorrect interpretation of Kirby's action and that Rivera & Svenson referenced this interpretation within the erroneous notation of their figure plate but have the correct taxonomic summary listed within the body of their text.

Discussion. The first known occurrence of this species being found in the United States took place in July 2014, when a juvenile individual was discovered by a student who was cataloguing the diversity of ants in Coconut Creek, Florida. This later instar nymph was initially believed by the student to belong to *Mantoida maya*, an unrelated species whose nymphs are also myrmecomorphic as in *Acontista*. The juvenile specimen was photographed and retained alive, where it was subsequently reared to adulthood at the student's home. Later that same year, in August 2014, another student found an adult female at the same location where the nymph was discovered in Coconut Creek. This specimen was also retained alive and kept in captivity until it died a few days later. Both adult specimens were later sent to Gavin Svenson at the Cleveland Museum of Natural History, where they were identified by Julio Rivera as *Acontista cordillerae*.

It was postulated at the time of this account that the occurrence of this species in Broward County, Florida was isolated and not indicative of an established population, as no other specimens had been found since the initial discovery. Further, given that the

collection locale of these individuals is located near a botanical garden that imports a variety of Neotropical plants, it was speculated that a rogue ootheca had clandestinely arrived on an imported plant and that it had yielded the adventive individuals in question.

In August 2020, an adult female of this species was observed and photographed by Bobby Seals, the manager of Green Cay Nature Center & Wetlands—a scenic marsh birding site in Palm Beach County, Florida with a 1.5 mile-long boardwalk. Mr. Seals reportedly encountered the specimen while out on the boardwalk and momentarily handled and photographed the female before it flew off into the wetland. This observation has been confirmed as a second occurrence of *cordillerae* in southern Florida, which is twenty miles away from the initial reporting site, thereby confirming that this species is established in the United States. Although it remains possible that *cordillerae* was first introduced into the country via clandestine importation of organic products, it is also possible, given the expansive range of this species across Mexico, Central America and northern South America, that *cordillerae* is actually native to the state but has such a low population density that it has heretofore never been documented.

References. Serville (1839) pg 201; Saussure (1869) pgs 62-63; Saussure & Zehntner (1894) pg 136; Kirby (1904) pg 233; Hebard (1919) pgs 130-132; Giglio-Tos (1927) pg 504; Marshall (1975) pg 323; Rivera & Svenson (2020) pg 117-120; Anderson (2021) pgs 23-24

Description. Habitus small, moderately robust and squat in females, much more slender in males. Body color various shades of green, variably marked with lighter green and brownish-black.

Head capsule rather thick in both sexes. Vertex slightly to moderately convex with 2 vertical sulci, superior margin distinctly surpassing dorsal surface of compound eyes in female, slightly lower or level with compound eyes in male. Juxtaocular processes broadly rounded, slightly produced in female, rising just above compound eyes but remaining lower than vertex. Juxtaocular processes placed distinctively lower than vertex and dorsal surface of compound eyes in male, creating deep juxtaocular furrows and somewhat excavated appearance of vertex in dorsal aspect. Lower frons narrow, transverse, dimpled in middle, superior margin produced between antennae. Compound eyes oval, convex, slightly protruding forward, colored light green. Ocelli prominent in male, very much reduced in female. Antennae filiform, reaching base of pronotum in male, significantly shorter in female, colored greenish at base, remaining segments black. Pigmentation of head capsule greenish in males, occasionally darkened. Female head capsule light green with longitudinal darker green banding.

Pronotum moderately elongate, somewhat narrowed in male, more broadened in female, measuring slightly longer than forecoxae, surface and margins smooth. Prozona slightly longer than wide, spanning wider than base of metazona. Supracoxal dilation distinct, supracoxal sulcus deep. Metazona measuring shorter than forecoxae, strongly constricted in middle, lateral margins sinuate. Pigmentation of pronotum typically light green, occasionally with dark green midline and paler margins.

Prothoracic legs. Forecoxae prismatic, rather slender; anteroventral margin unarmed. Forefemora robust, dilated, elongate-triangular. Tibial spur placed between discoidal spines and first anteroventral spine when foretibiae is closed upon the forefemora; tibial spur groove absent. Forefemora with 5 posteroventral, 11-13 anteroventral, and 3 discoidal spines, all short and stout with black tips. Foretibiae long, slender, armed with 14-18 posteroventral and 11 anteroventral spines, all very short and contiguous, becoming indistinct toward base. Tibial spur well developed. Prothoracic legs typically pigmented monochromatic green, variably annulated with darker green. Dark phase individuals of either sex may have prothoracic legs infuscated brownish-black with variable lighter-colored banding. Tarsomeres terminated with blackish.

Meso/metathoracic legs somewhat shortened with thickened femora. Coloration of male legs typically light green with femoral apices and adjacent portions of corresponding tibiae brownish-black. Legs occasionally immaculate. Female legs light green, annulated with darker green.

Wings. Male forewings somewhat broadened, surpassing tip of abdomen in length. Pigmentation variable, typically hyaline with light green venation. Forewings may have sizable blackish blotch in basal fourth of discoidal area that extends to stigma with remainder of wing hyaline to lightly infumated. Some individuals may also have additional concentration of infumation forming partial median band from costal ridge, together with third preapical band. Costal area narrow, proximally dilated, partially to fully opaque green, becoming subhyaline toward apices. Opaque green coloration of costal area may encroach into base of discoidal area. Stigma prominent, brownish-black,

rounded to trigonal. Venation configuring irregular squarish cells across discoidal area. Female forewings spindle-shaped, reaching to abdominal terminalia, costal area dilated at base, quickly narrowing toward apices. Forewings opaque in basal three-quarters, abruptly turning membranous hyaline in distal fourth. Basal pigmentation olive green, crossed by 2 crescent-shaped maculations of pale greenish-white with two additional oblique maculations near termination of opaque coloration. Stigma prominent, more or less rounded, brownish to black. Pigmentation of male hindwings highly variable. Typical coloration involves blackish-brown banding in basal half of anal area. Extent of hindwing maculation ranging from having irregular blackish band arising from posterior margin of anal area, partially to fully extending to discoidal area in basal third, to having entire basal half of wing darkened. Extreme base of anal area and costal margin dark red with brownish venation throughout. Light phase individuals may have hindwings entirely hyaline with greenish costal margin and greenish venation throughout. Entire surface of hindwings iridescent regardless of extent of maculation. Female hindwings protruding out from forewings. Costal, discoidal, and basal third of anal area deep red, reddish-orange or bright yellow, bordered by wide, blackish-brown submarginal band with whitish venation. Submarginal band occasionally incomplete, not reaching costal margin, broken into small blotch in discoidal field. Extreme posterior margin and apices hyaline.

Abdomen. Male abdomen slender, elongated; female abdomen dilated. Abdominal sternites greenish, tergites reddish in the middle with greenish margins. Female has lateral margins of tergites dilated outward beneath wings, demonstrating alternating light and dark green pigmentation of segments. Supra-anal plate large, strongly transverse, spanning two times wider than long, feebly bilobate. Subgenital plate elongate-triangular with small emargination. Cerci very small, conical, measuring twice as long as supra-anal plate.

Measurements. (All measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) *Male.* Body length 19-20.5; pronotum length 5-6; forewing length 14-21; prothoracic femur length 4.5-5.5; metathoracic femur length 5. *Female.* Body length 21-26; pronotum length 6-6.5; forewing length 14.5-18; prothoracic femur length 6.5-7.

Biological Notes. *Oothecae* are barrel-shaped. Distal end extended into lengthy point. Proximal end flattened against substrate, often surrounded by a pad of residual material. Lateral surface ribbed throughout, delimiting between 6-10 egg chambers. External wall porous and spongy, pigmented light tan when fresh, turning yellowish-brown with age. Emergence area consisting of 12-18 sealed openings that are placed along lateral surface. *Oothecae* are attached at the proximal end, so that they sit with the ventral and dorsal surfaces positioned vertically, entirely exposed.

Development. Nymph emergence is extended and takes place approximately 26 days after oviposition of ootheca with no diapause period in between, oftentimes while maternal female is still alive. Early instar nymphs are myrmecomorphic, having head capsule, metazona, and meso/metathorax colored reddish-brown with thoracic segments edged in whitish along posterior margin. Prozona and vertex contrastingly pigmented dark brownish-black. Compound eyes dark gray. Abdomen brownish-red with gray sheen of fine setae. Antennae grayish-black with patch of 5-6 antennomeres turning white in basal third before transitioning back to black near base. All legs reddish-brown with femora largely brownish-black in basal portion. Forecoxae often with ring of grayish-white in basal half. Later instar nymphs typically retain same general color pattern as

younger instars, continually growing reddish-brown to greenish overall with each consecutive instar.

Adulthood. Adults occur in late summer and are infrequently found amid ground cover and low shrubbery.

Reproduction. This species is spontaneous parthenogenetic, in that females are noted to be capable of asexually reproducing offspring that are inviable and will die prior to reaching maturity. Unmated females may produce oothecae that yield between 5-10 inviable nymphs.

Ethology. When not lying in wait for prey, nymphs readily move about foliage in a swift manner, mimicking the behavior of an ant. Their antennae quiver incessantly, especially when they ambulate, but also when their body is at rest. As with other species of *Acontista*, individuals position their forelegs with coxae held forward, nearly perpendicular to pronotum when clasped closed at repose. Both sexes are amply winged and can take flight. Males are much more agile than the heavier bodied females and are attracted to lights at night.

References. Saussure (1869) pgs 62-63; Saussure (1871a) pgs 34-36; Saussure (1872a) pgs 239-240; Saussure & Zehntner (1894) pgs 135-138; Kirby (1904) pg 233; Rehn (1904c) pgs 561-562; Hebard (1919) pgs 130-132; Giglio-Tos (1927) pgs 502-504, 507; Hebard (1932a) pg 213; Rehn (1935b) pgs 256-259; Hughes-Schrader (1950) pg 26; Svenson (2016) pers. comm.; Fridie (2018) pers. comm.; Rivera (2020) pers. comm.; Seals (2020) pers. comm.; Rivera & Svenson (2020) pg 120

U.S./Canadian Distribution Range of *Acontista cordillerae*

01, *Acontista cordillerae* adult female. Boynton Beach, Palm Beach Co, FL 08.25.20

02, *Acontista cordillerae* adult female. Boynton Beach, Palm Beach Co, FL 08.25.20

Contributing Photographer.

01, *Acontista cordillerae* adult female
Photographed by Bobby Seals

02, *Acontista cordillerae* adult female
Photographed by Bobby Seals

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